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Research Article

**ANTI-BACTERIAL ACTIVITY AND PHYTOCHEMICAL
COMPONENTS OF LEAF EXTRACT OF *PINUS LONGIFOLIA***Sk Samim Akhtar*, Mrs. P.Geetha Vani¹, Dr. D Venkata Ramana¹

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Abstract:

The technique improves patient compliance by reducing both dose and the frequency of administration and thus minimizing the local as well as systemic toxic effects. The aim of the present research work was to of Methanolic extracts of *Nymphaea stellata* in the doses of 50 mg/kg, 100 mg/kg, and 200 mg/kg were used in Wistar rats of either sex. Were measured by standard biochemical methods. Silymarin (500 mg/kg) was used as a standard drug for assessment of Anti-Microbial status. When compared with the standard Anti-Microbial agent Ciprofloxacin, The antibacterial activity of these prepared nanoparticles against pathogenic bacterium has shown.

The anti-inflammatory activity was determined by carrageenan-induced paw edema rat. The results demonstrated that *Nymphaea stellata* is effective for both acute and chronic inflammation. Thus, these results have suggested that *Nymphaea stellata* possesses anti-inflammatory activities.

Keywords: - Anti-Microbial agent, anti-inflammatory activity, *Nymphaea*.

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INTRODUCTION:

Medicinal plants are part and parcel of human society to combat diseases, from the dawn of civilization^{1,2}. They usually contain many biologically active ingredients and are used primarily for treating mild or chronic ailments. According to World Health Organization (WHO), about 80% of the world population relies chiefly on the plant based traditional medicine especially for their primary healthcare needs. Herbal medicines are in great demand in the developed as well as developing countries for primary healthcare because of their wide biological and medicinal activities, higher safety margins and lesser costs^{3,4}. Infectious diseases are a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. The number of multi-drug resistant microbial strains and the appearance of strains with reduced susceptibility to antibiotics are continuously increasing. This increase has been attributed to indiscriminate use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, immunosuppressive agents, intravenous catheters, organ transplantation and ongoing epidemics of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infections^{5,6}. This situation provided the impetus to the search for new antimicrobial substances from various sources like medicinal plants. Synthetic drugs are not only expensive and inadequate for the treatment of diseases but are also often with adulterations and side effects. Therefore, there is a need to search for new infection-fighting strategies to control microbial infections⁷.

Plant medicines are used on a worldwide scale to prevent and treat infectious diseases⁸. Plants are rich in a wide variety of secondary metabolites such as tannins, alkaloids, terpenoids and flavonoids having been found in vitro since they have antimicrobial properties and may serve as an alternative, effective, cheap and safe antimicrobial for the treatment of microbial infections⁹. Plant based antimicrobial compounds have great therapeutic potential as they have lesser side effects as compared with synthetic drugs and also little chance of development of resistance. Therefore an attempt has been made to study the antibacterial activity of ten medicinally important plants viz. *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, *Berberis aristata*, *Chromolaena odorata*, *Embelia ribes*, *Jasminum angustifolia*, *Mahonia leschenaultii*, *Pluchea lanceolata*, *Plumbago indica*, *Terminalia chebula*, *Vitex negundo*.¹⁰

INTRODUCTION OF BACTERIA

Clinical isolated bacteria used in the study are *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Escherichia coli

Classification

Escherichia coli is the most commonly encountered member of the family Enterobacteriaceae in the normal colonic flora and the most common cause of opportunistic infections. All members of the family Enterobacteriaceae are facultative, all ferment glucose and reduce nitrates to nitrites and all are oxidase negative.¹¹

Table-1 Classification of *E. coli*

Domain	Bacteria
Phylum	Proteobacteria
Class	Gammaproteobacteria
Order	Enterobacteriales
Family	Enterobacteriaceae
Genus	<i>Escherichia</i>
Species	<i>coli</i>

Figure 1.7: Gram stain of *E. coli*.

Morphology and identification

Escherichia coli is gram-negative, non-sporing bacilli with most strains being motile and generally possessing both sex pili and adhesive fimbriae. Because most strains rapidly ferment lactose, colonies grown on MacConkey media are smooth, glossy, and translucent and are rose-pink in colour. Some strains grown on on blood agar result in colonies being surrounded by zones of haemolysis. Colonies are smooth, circular, 1 – 1.5mm in diameter and yellow opaque if lactose fermenting (blue, if non-lactose fermenting) when grown on cystine-lactose-electrolyte deficient (CLED) medium.¹²

Epidemiology

Strains of *Escherichia coli* predominate among the aerobic commensal bacteria present in the healthy gut.¹³

Escherichia coli Infections

Escherichia coli was initially considered a non-harmful member of the colon flora, but is now associated with a wide range of diseases and infections

including meningeal, gastrointestinal, urinary tract, wound and bacteremia infections in all age groups.¹⁴ Other infections caused by *Escherichia coli* include peritonitis, cholecystitis, septic wounds and bedsores. They may also infect the lower respiratory passages or cause bacteraemia and endotoxic shock especially in surgical or debilitated patients.¹⁵

Antimicrobial Susceptibility

Within the community, *Escherichia coli* strains are commonly susceptible to all agents active against the Enterobacteriaceae. However, because of the frequent occurrence of R plasmids, strains acquired in hospitals may be resistant to any combination of potentially effective antimicrobics and therapy must therefore be guided by susceptibility testing.¹⁶

Staphylococcus aureus

Classification

Members of the genus *Staphylococcus* (staphylococci) are Gram-positive cocci that tend to be arranged in grape-like clusters.¹⁷

Table-2 Classification of *S. aureus*

Domain	Bacteria
Phylum	Firmicutes
Class	Bacilli
Order	Bacillales
Family	Staphylococcaceae
Genus	<i>Staphylococcus</i>
Species	<i>aureus</i>

Figure 1.8: Gram stain of *S. aureus*

Morphology and identification

Staphylococci are spherical cells about 1 μm in diameter arranged in irregular clusters. Single cocci, pairs, tetrads, and chains are also seen in liquid cultures. Young cocci stain strongly gram-positive; on aging, many cells become gram-negative. Staphylococci are non-motile and do not form spores.

Staphylococcus aureus is a facultative anaerobe that grows at an optimum temperature of 37°C and an optimum pH of 7.5.

S. aureus produces white colonies that tend to turn a buff-golden color with time, which is the basis of the species epithet aureus (golden). Most, but not all, strains show a rim of clear β-hemolysis surrounding the colony.

On nutrient agar, following aerobic incubation for 24 hours at 37°C, colonies are 1 – 3mm in diameter, have a smooth glistening surface, an entire edge and an opaque pigmented appearance. In most strains, pigmentation is golden with orange, yellow and cream varieties. On MacConkey agar, colonies are small to medium in size and pink or pink-orange in colour.

Epidemiology

Staphylococci are highly successful colonizers of humans and animals. They reside mainly on the skin, particularly in moist areas such as the anterior nares (nose), axilla and groin. Between one-third and three-quarters of individuals carry these organisms at any one time. Staphylococcal infections occur worldwide, and newly emerging hypervirulent or multiresistant strains spread rapidly over wide geographical areas. The bacteria survive in the air, on objects or in dust for days, therefore they can contaminate environments (such as hospitals) and continue to be transmitted over long periods of time. Some individuals may shed the organism more heavily than others. Staphylococcal infections are acquired from either self (endogenous) or external (exogenous) sources.¹⁸

Infections

S. aureus causes serious infections of the skin, soft tissues, bone, lung, heart, brain or blood. include pneumonia, bacteremia leading to secondary pneumonia and endocarditis, osteomyelitis secondary to bacteremia and septic arthritis, seen in children and in patients with a history of rheumatoid arthritis. Diseases caused

by Staphylococcal toxins include scalded skin syndrome and toxic shock syndrome.¹⁹

Antimicrobial Susceptibility

Resistance to penicillin G can be predicted by a positive test for β-lactamase; approximately 90% of *S. aureus* produce β-lactamase. Resistance to nafcillin (and oxacillin and methicillin) occurs in about 35% of *S. aureus* and approximately 75% of *S. epidermidis* isolates.

Alternative antibiotics for resistant organisms (e.g. MRSA) include vancomycin, erythromycin and gentamicin. Some strains become resistant to multiple antibiotics.²⁰

Pseudomonas aeruginosa**Classification**

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a classic opportunist pathogen belonging to the genus *Pseudomonas*.

Domain	Bacteria
Phylum	Proteobacteria
Class	Gammaproteobacteria
Order	Pseudomonadales
Family	Pseudomonadaceae
Genus	<i>Pseudomonas</i>
Species	<i>aeruginosa</i>

Figure 1.9: Gram stain of *P. aeruginosa* cells

Morphology and Identification

Is obligate aerobe, motile, rod-shaped, measuring about 0.6 x 2 µm. It is gram-negative and occurs as single bacteria, in pairs, and occasionally in short chains. sometimes producing a sweet or grape-like or corn taco-like odor.²¹

Its production of blue, yellow, or rust-colored pigments differentiates it from most other Gram-negative bacteria. The blue pigment, **pyocyanin**, is produced only by *P.aeruginosa*. **Fluorescin**, a yellow pigment that fluoresces under ultraviolet light, is by *P. aeruginosa* and other free-living less pathogenic *Pseudomonas* species. Pyocyanin produced and fluorescin combined produce a bright green color that diffuses throughout the medium.²²

P aeruginosa grows well at 37–42 °C; its growth at 42 °C helps differentiate it from other *Pseudomonas* species. It does not ferment carbohydrates, but many strains oxidize glucose.²³

Epidemiology

P. aeruginosa normally inhabit soil, water, and vegetation and can be isolated from the skin, throat, and stool of healthy persons. They often colonize hospital food, sinks, taps, mops, and respiratory equipment. Spread is from patient to patient via contact with fomites or by ingestion of contaminated food and water.

Infections

Pseudomonas aeruginosa causes infections in healthy individuals and those who are hospitalized or have a compromised immune system as a result of other diseases. A variety of human infections are commonly associated with this bacterium:

- Urinary tract infections
- Ventilator-associated pneumonia
- Surgical site infection
- Respiratory infections
- Ocular infections
- Ear infections (external otitis, malignant external otitis)
- Skin and soft tissue infections, including hot tub folliculitis, and osteomyelitis
- Burn sepsis

Individuals with compromising conditions, such as HIV/AIDS, cystic fibrosis, chemotherapy-related neutropenia, and diabetes have an increased risk of acquiring an infection and developing complications.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is frequently resistant to many commonly used antibiotics. Although many strains are susceptible to gentamicin, tobramycin, colistin, and amikacin, resistant forms have developed, making susceptibility testing essential.²⁴

Antibiotic resistance

The discovery of antibiotics in the mid-twentieth century revolutionized the management and treatment of infectious disease caused by bacteria. Infections that would normally have been fatal were now curable. Since then, antimicrobial agents (antibiotics and related medicinal drugs acting on bacteria, viruses, fungi and parasites) have saved the lives and eased the suffering of millions of people. Today, antibiotics are crucial not only for the treatment of bacterial infections, but also for prophylactic coverage of high risk patients e.g. those in intensive care, organ transplants, cancer chemotherapy and prenatal care. However, these gains are now seriously jeopardised by the rapid emergence and spread of microbes that are resistant to antimicrobials.

The mass production of penicillin in 1943 dramatically reduced illness and death from infectious diseases caused by bacteria. However, within four years, bacteria began appearing that could resist the action of penicillin. Pharmaceutical companies fought back by developing other types of antibiotics. After more than 50 years of widespread use of these “miracle drugs”, antibiotics are no longer as effective as they once were. Virtually all important bacterial infections in throughout the world are becoming resistant. And even though pharmacological industries have produced a number of new antibiotics in the last three decades, resistance to these drugs by microorganisms has increased. In general, bacteria have the genetic ability to transmit and acquire resistance to drugs, which are utilized as therapeutic agents.²⁵

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Plant collection and identification

Pinus longifolia is an aromatic much branched erect herb with 4 angled stems, bearded nodes leaves. It is a common weed of open lands. For the present study fresh plants were collected from locality and brought to laboratory in air tight polythene bags for further processing.

Preparation of leaf extract

For the preparation of leaf extract, fresh leaves were collected in a beaker and washed several times with water to remove the dust and finally with double distilled water. 10 g washed leaves were cut into fine pieces and crushed with the help of mortar and pestle in 100 ml double distilled water. After grinding the aqueous extract was taken in 250 ml beaker and boiled for 10 min at 80 °C temperature. The plant extract was allowed to cool at room temperature and then filtered with whatman filter paper. The filtrate was centrifuged for 20–25 min at 10000 rpm, the supernatant was collected and stored at 4 °C. This filtrate was used as a stabilizing and reducing agents.

Phytochemical analysis

The Methanolic extract of *Pinus longifolia* were subjected to qualitative phytochemical tests for different constituents such as alkaloids, carbohydrates, glycosides, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, proteins, and free aminoacids and triterpenoids.

1. Test for carbohydrate

Small quantity of extract was dissolved in 5ml of water and filtered.

Molisch test

The filtrate was treated with a few drops of α - naphthol (20% in ethyl alcohol). Then 1 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 was added along the sides of inclined test tube

and observed for formation of violet coloured ring at the interface.

1. Test for glycosides and anthroquinones Borntrager's test

A small amount of Methanolic extract was hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid for few hours on water bath and the hydrosylate was extracted with benzene. The benzene layer was treated with dilute ammonia solution and observed for the formation of reddish pink colour.

Legal test

The extract was dissolved in pyridine and made alkaline with few drops of 10% NaOH and freshly prepared sodium nitroprusside was added and observed for formation of blue colour.

1. Test for flavonoids Ammonia test

Filter paper strips were dipped in the dilute solution of the extract, ammoniated and observed for colour change from white to yellow.

1. Test for Tannins and Phenolic compounds

The extract was dissolved in distilled water and dissolved into three portions. Sodium chloride (10%) was added to one portion, 1% gelatine to second portion and gelatine salt reagent to third portion. Precipitation with later or both gelatin salt reagents was indicative of the presence of tannins. Precipitation with salt solution indicates a false positive test. Positive tests were further confirmed by the addition of a few drops of dilute ferric chloride (1% $FeCl_3$) to the test extract which gave blue or green black coloration.

Test for Proteins and Aminoacids

Small amount of extract was dissolved in distilled water and filtered.

Biuret's test

To the ammoniated alkaline filtrate add 2-3 drops of 0.002% copper sulphate and observed for appearance of red or violet colour.

Millon's test

To 2 ml of filtrate 5-6 drops of millons reagent (1 g of mercury + 9 ml of fuming nitric acid solution) was added and observed for red precipitates.

Ninhydrin test

To the filtrate lead acetate solution was added to precipitate tannins and filtered. The filtrate was spotted on paper chromatogram and sprayed with ninhydrin reagent and heated at 110°C for five minutes and observed for red or violet colour.

Xanthoprotein test

To the filtrate a few drops concentrated nitric acid was added by the side of test tube and observed for appearance of yellow colour.

Test for sterols and triterpenes

The extract was refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide until the completion of saponification. Then the mixture was diluted with distilled water and extracted with diethyl ether. The ethereal extract was evaporated and the unsaponifiable matter was subjected to the following tests.

Libermann- Buchard's test

The ether soluble residue was dissolved in chloroform and a few drops of acetic anhydride was added followed by a few drops concentrated sulphuric acid from sides of the test tube and observed for the formation of blue to blue- red colour.

Salkowski's reaction

To the ether soluble residue 2 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was added and observed for the formation of yellow ring at the junction which turns red after one minute.

ANTI- MICROBIAL ACTIVITY STUDIES ON EXTRACT AND FRACTIONS OF PINUS LONGIFOLIA

Physical nature and percentage yield of extracts

The percentage yield and physical status of the methanolic leaf extract (MEPL) and chloroform (CSC) and aqueous fractions *Pinus longifolia* are showed in the TABLE Yield of the extracts calculated with reference of the weight raw material used. For fractions, the yield was calculated with respect to corresponding methanolic extract.

Table-6.2: Percentage yield and physical status of the methanolic extract and fractions of *Tulasi*

Extract/Fraction	Code	Yield (%)
Methanolic	MEBM	12.5
Ethyl acetate	BME	6.5
Chloroform	BMC	5.3
n-hexane	BMH	6.1
Aqueous	BMQ	3.3

Antibacterial action:

Antibacterial activity

Generally the antibacterial activity of a compound is expressed in terms of its ability to inhibit the growth of bacteria in nutrient broth or agar media. The bacterial growth inhibition can be measured by two methods.

- Cup plate method
- Serial dilution method

Bacterial Culture medium:

Nutrient broth has been used for the preparation of inoculum of the bacteria and nutrient agar is used for the evaluation of antibacterial activity.

Antibacterial activity

Antibacterial activity by Cup plate Agar Diffusion method by measuring the zone of inhibition in mm.

Materials:

- Nutrient Broth Media
- Nutrient Agar media
- Streptomycin (standard)
- Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO)
- Distilled Water

Required Equipment:

- Laminar air flow cabin
- Incubator
- Refrigerator
- Micropipettes
- Culture plates
- Boiling tube
- Eppendorf tubes

Evaluation for Antimicrobial Activity:

The antibacterial activity of substituted chalcones (3a-3e) and their derivatives 4,6-diaryl oxazines (4a-4d) had been assayed against four different strains of bacteria by cup-plate agar diffusion method by measuring the zone of inhibition.

Table 6.3: Composition of the nutrient agar medium:

Peptone	5gm
Sodium chloride	5gm
Beef extract	1.5gm
Yeast extract	1.5gm
Agar	1.5gm
Distilled water up to	1000mL
pH	7.4±0.2

Procedure:

The test organisms were sub cultured using nutrient broth medium. The tubes containing sterilized medium were inoculated with respective bacterial strains. After incubation at 37±1°C for 24 hours they were stored in refrigerator. The stock cultures were maintained. Bacterial inoculum was prepared by transferring a

loopful of culture to nutrient broth in conical flask. The flasks were incubated at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 48 hours before the experimentation.

Solution of test compound was prepared by dissolving the sample in DMSO. A reference standard for both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria was made by dissolving accurately weighed quantity of Moxifloxacin and Streptomycin in sterile distilled water.

The nutrient agar medium was sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 15min. The petriplate, tubes and flasks plugged with cotton were sterilized in hot air oven at 160°C for an two hours. Into each sterilized petriplate, about 25mL of molten nutrient agar medium inoculated with the respective strains of bacteria was transferred aseptically. The plates were left at room temperature to allow solidification. In each plate, cups of 5 mm diameter were made with sterile borer. Then 100 μl of the test solution was added to the respective cups aseptically and labeled accordingly. The plates were kept undisturbed for at least 2 hours in refrigerator to allow diffusion of the solution properly into the nutrient agar medium. After the incubation of the plates at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 hours, the diameter of the zone of inhibition surrounding each of the cups was measured with the help of the scale and tabulated.

Standard drugs used : Streptomycin, Moxifloxacin

ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

Animals

Swiss albino mice weighing 20-25 gm wistar rats weighing 150- 200 gm were used for this study. The animals were obtained from animal house. On arrival, the animals were placed randomly and allocated to

treatment groups in polypropylene cages with paddy husk as bedding. Animals were housed at a temperature of $24\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and relative humidity of 30-70%. A12: 12 light: day cycle was followed. All animals were allowed to free access to water and bed with standard commercial pelleted chow. All the experimental procedures are protocols used in this study were reviewed by Institutional Animal Ethics Committee.

Acute Toxicity Studies

The acute toxicity was performed according to OECD guidelines

423. The selected albino rats were used for toxicity studies. The animals were divided into five groups of three in each. The animals were fasted overnight prior to the acute experimental procedure. Extract was given orally to rats at the graded doses like 10, 30, 100, & 300 mg/ kg body weight. Immediately, after dosing, the animals were observed continuously for first four hours for behavioural changes were closely observed for hyperactivity, ataxia, convulsion, salivation, tremors, diarrhoea, lethargy, sleep. They were then kept under observation up to 14 days after drug administration to determine the mortality, if any. One-tenth and one-fifth of the maximum tolerated dose (200 and 400 mg/ kg, body weight) of Methanol leaf extract of *Nymphaea stellata*. Selected to evaluate analgesic, anti-inflammatory and antipyretic activity studies in rats.

Statistical analysis

The values of statistical analysis were expressed as mean values \pm SEM. The results of the experiment were performed as changes of percentage from control value. Data was analyzed by ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison tests. $p\leq 0.05$ was considered to be statistical significance.

RESULTS:

Table: Qualitative phytochemical Evaluation of *Pinus longifolia*.

Parameters	value
1. Alkaloid	+
2. Carbohydrates	+
3. Glycosides	-
4. Flavonoids	++
5. Tannins & Phenolic compounds	+
6. Proteins & Amino acids	+
7. Saponins	+
8. Sterols or Triterpenes	+

++: high content, +: moderate, -: Negative,

From the qualitative phytochemical analysis of ethanolic extract of *Pinus longifolia*. It content alkaloids, Tannins, phenolic compound, sterols, saponins, protein and amino acids and high amount of flavonoids.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS ON ANTI-MICROBIALB ACTIVITY:

Table: Zone of inhibition of solvent extract of *Pinus longifolia* against *E.Coli*:

Compounds	50µg/ml (mm)	100µg/ml (mm)	1000µg/ml (mm)
MEBM	6	10	12
BME	10	12	16
BMC	11	15	18
BMH	8	10	14
BMQ	12	18	20
CPN	12	16	20
MXN	14	18	24

BMEFigure: Zone of inhibition of solvent extract of *Pinus longifolia* against *E.Coli*

Table: Zone of inhibition of *Pinus longifolia* against on *Streptococcus aureus*:

Compounds	50µg/ml	100µg/ml	1000µg/ml
MEBM	5 mm	9 mm	14 mm
BME	10 mm	12 mm	18 mm
BMC	6 mm	10 mm	15 mm
BMH	10 mm	12 mm	14 mm
BMQ	6 mm	10 mm	16 mm
CPN	14 mm	18 mm	22 mm
MXN	16 mm	20 mm	24 mm

Figure: Zone of inhibition of *Pinus longifolia* against on *Streptococcus aureus*:

Results and discussions of Antimicrobial Activity:

The Extracted compounds **MEBM, BME, BMC, BMH, BMQ** has been evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus, Bacillus subtilis*) and Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli, Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) bacteria by measuring the zone of inhibition. The results have been compared with a broad spectrum antibacterial agent Ciprofloxacin as standard drug.

- All the Extracted compounds (BMC & BMQ), were found to be effective antibacterial agents.
- The compounds MEBM showed minimum activity against *E.coli* with zone of inhibition 6mm, 10mm, 12mm.
- The compounds BMC showed maximum activity against Gram positive bacteria *E. Coli* at 100µg/ml with zone of inhibition 15mm. Among all those compounds, MEBM, BMC and BMQ showed Poor activity against Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) with zone of inhibition of 5mm, 6mm and 5mm.

CONCLUSION:

Evaluation of Anti-Bacterial effect Methanolic leaves extract of *Pinus longifolia*. Deals with the exploration of pharmacological and phytochemical screening of the selected Indian medicinal plant *Pinus longifolia*.

The method used for Methanolic extract was found to be simple and reproducible. The Methanolic extract of *Pinus longifolia* demonstrated significant Anti-Microbial properties in experimental animals in this study. These activities may be attributed to the various Phytoconstituents of Methanolic extract of *Pinus longifolia* such as flavonoids, tannins, saponins, alkaloids, anthocyanins, glycosides, polyphenols, and steroids. However, further experimental studies are required to explore the exact mechanism of actions and next level of clinical trials to generate novel drugs. This might prove helpful to use its immense therapeutic efficacy as a potent Anti-Microbial phytochemistry.

The *Pinus longifolia* has shown significant Anti-Bacterial effects. These effects maybe because of the presence of phytochemicals such as flavonoids, tannins and Terpenoids present in the plant extract.

The Present study showed that the Methanolic leaves extract of *Pinus longifolia*, posses peripheral and central Anti-Bacterial activity in animal model. The *Pinus longifolia* leaves extract showed Anti-Bacterial activity in different animal model. Flavonoids and tannins are the major constituents of *Pinus longifolia*

leaves, which may be responsible for its Anti-Bacterial activity.

Further detailed study on *Pinus longifolia plant* using different flogestic agents in this area will enable us to understand the mechanism of action underline the above mention activity.

REFERENCES:

1. B. Nitha, A.B. Remashree and Indira Balachandran. Antibacterial Activity Of Some Selected Indian Medicinal Plants. IJPSR, 2012; Vol. 3(7): 2038-2042.
2. Chaudhary G, Goyal S, Poonia P. Lawsonia inermis Linnaeus: A Phytopharmacological Review. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research 2010; 2(2): 91-98.
3. Goyal BR, Goyal RK, Mehta AA. Phyto-Pharmacognosy of Archyranthes aspera: A Review. Pharmacognosy Reviews 2008; 1:1.
4. Cragg GM, Newman DJ, Sander KM. Natural products in drug discovery and development. Journal of Natual Products 1997; 60:52-60.
5. Dean DA, Burchard KW. Fungal infection in surgical patients. American Journal of Surgery 1996; 171: 374-382.
6. Gonzalez CE, Venzon D, Lee S et al. Risk factors for fungemia in children infected with human immunodeficiency virus: a case control study. Clinical Infectious Diseases 1996; 23: 515-521.
7. VaghasiyaY, Chanda SV Screening of Methanol and Acetone Extracts of Fourteen Indian Medicinal Plants for Antimicrobial Activity. Turkish Journal of Biology 2007; 31:243-248.
8. Soulsby EJ. Resistance to antimicrobials in humans and animals. British Journal of Medicine 2005; 331: 1219-1220.
9. Cowan MM. Plant products as antimicrobial agents. Clinical Microbiology Reviews 1999; 12: 564-82.
10. Udayan PS, Balachandran I: Medicinal Plants of Arya Vaidya Sala Herb Garden. Department of Publication Arya Vaidya Sala, Firt Edition 2009.
11. Tirtha SS, "The Ayurveda Encyclopedia-Natural Secrets to Healing, Prevention and Longevity", 2007.
12. S. Chaudhari, N. Shaikh, "Gaduchi-the best ayurvedic herb", The Pharma Innovation Journal, 2(4), 97-102, 2013. International Journal of Scientific Research and Review Volume 7, Issue 12, 2018 ISSN NO: 2279-543X Page No: 593.
13. U. Spandana, S.L. Ali, T. Nirmala, M. Santhi, S.D. SipaiBabu , "A Review on Tinosporacordifolia", International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research, 4(2), 61-68, 2013.

14. KN. Aiyer, M. Kolammal, Pharmacognosy of Ayurvedic Drugs, Series 1. 1st ed Trivendram, The central Research institute, 1963.

15. KR. Kirtikar and BD. Basu, Indian Medicinal Plants. Second Edition, International Book Distributers, Dehradun, 2005.